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In the life and work of Ivo Andrić, the Serbian writer and Nobel Prize winner, there are many different kinds of “East” and “West”. There were Byzantium and the Roman Empire, Orthodox and Catholic religion, the Islamic East and the Christian West, the Balkans and Europe. The aim of this work is to present the basis of all the different oppositions that comprise Andrić’s life and work,¹ while at the same time searching for the answers to the questions concerning how close was Andrić’s approach to that of the European intellectuals of his time.²

1. Andrić – from a student to a diplomat and a writer

Ivo Andrić was born in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Travnik) in 1892 in one of the provinces which was then under the control of Austria-Hungary. He graduated from the gymnasium in Sarajevo. There he was the president of the Society of Serbo-Croatian youth (later renamed into The Young Bosnia movement),³ which had a pan-slavic programme that aimed to break the Austro-Hungarian country and unite The South Slavs under the hat of Serbia, that was already free by then. His home Bosnia (which was first under the Turkish reign for centuries, and throughout the second part of 19th century under the Austro-Hungarian reign), which developed as a spiritual entity upon the civilization dividing line between the East and West, represents the main theme in many Andrić’s novels.

As a European student, politically engaged intellectual (Zagreb, Vienna, Krakow) and later a Yugoslav diplomat in foreign countries (Graz, Rome, Trieste, Berlin), Andrić had the opportunity to

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¹ A great number of literary criticism provides valuable analyses from different aspects and in different times, regarding the existence of East and West in Andrić’s works. In this work, I particularly used the works of two authors, Isidora Sekulić (Секулић 1923) and Ji-Hyang Kim (김 1998), which are opposed to each other in many aspects.

² For this purpose I also included the analysis of Rebecca West’s book, the famous writer and travel writer of Irish-Scottish origin (1892-1983), which bears the title *Black Lamb and Grey Falcon* (West 2008), as well as pieces of work of the Swiss Archibald Rudolph Reiss (1875-1929) which I had the opportunity to incorporate in my previous work (Радић 2005).

³ In the early 20th century, and for decades latter, for political reasons, the term “Serbian” was usually replaced with “Serbo-Croatian” in the regions where the Serbs lived.

get to know the spirit of Europe very well, especially the spirit of Western Europe. However, owing to his being a political dissident and a member of the revolutionary movement The Young Bosnia, throughout almost the entire period of World War I he had been a prisoner in Austro-Hungarian jails (Slovenia, Croatia), and also in a home confinement in a village of Ovčarevo near Travnik, in a friar environment (Брајовић 2004: 69). By 1919, after the ruin of Austro-Hungarian Empire and the creation of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, Andrić moves to Belgrade. In Belgrade he entered the diplomatic office of the new Yugoslav country, where he remained until the beginning of the World War II, while he was also working on his books. Andrić observed Yugoslav monarchy as an opportunity for a number of the South Slavic people to finally break free from the negative, several centuries long Turkish heritage, and return into the European civilization, through their own country. The open-minded European intellectuals also pinned their hopes on the Kingdom of Yugoslavia (cf. West 2008: 457).

During World War II, Andrić spent his time in Belgrade, and by 1945, after the war ended, he published his novels *The Bridge on the Drina*, *The Chronicles of Travnik*, *The woman from Sarajevo*. The following year he became the member of Serbian Academy of Science. In 1958 he was nominated for the Nobel Prize by the Association of Yugoslav writers, as well as M. Krleža (on the Croatian side) (Брајовић 2004: 164, 155). He won the Nobel Prize for his novel *The Bridge on the Drina* in 1961 (cf. Kim / Radić 2009).⁴ Andrić was a holder of an honorary degree of the University of Belgrade, and he bequeathed his literary heritage to the Serbian Academy of Science and Art. His connection to Belgrade and Serbia, which is several decades long, left a permanent impress on his life and work “not just in formal aspect, but in essence”, as he himself said (according to Поповић 1991: 91). This includes Belgrade-related literary topics, along with his early adopting of ekavian dialect in literary language, which is a trademark of the literary tradition of the Eastern Serbs (Радић 2006). The most prominent basic characteristics of Andrić’s work are “homeland of Bosnia, Serbian literary tradition, Yugoslav political ideology of his generation” (Деретић 1983: 559).

2. Andrić – the historian

As an intellectual and a writer from the Balkans, Andrić strived to see through all of the important cultural features of the Eastern and Western civilizations, which were specifically opposed and interwoven throughout the long Medieval period in the region of his homeland Bosnia. He was famous for his work in studying the Turkish historic sources, especially the Islamic religion and its influence on Bosnia. He dealt with this topic in his thesis *The development of spiritual life in Bosnia under the influence of Turkish rule* (cf. Андрић 1995) which he presented in Graz in 1924. Although,

⁴ The Yugoslav public, “above all, Serbian”, greeted this event warmly (Поповић 1991: 104).

generally speaking, the scientific evaluation of Andrić's thesis were not particularly high, the ideological reflections on his work still attract attention, as well as the ideological environment in which its evaluators work.⁵

In the first chapter of his thesis (*Prehistory, The spiritual life in Bosnia prior to the Turkish invasion*), Andrić dealt with the religion of old Bosnian Bogomils, who had their separate religious organization long throughout the Medieval period. This organization (also known as the Bosnian church) was opposed to both Catholic and Orthodox churches, and it preserved a kind of dualistic belief, which originates from the Middle East.⁶ This "Eastern origin and the strong exclusiveness of the Bogomils" was one of the first barriers against "forced entrance of the influence of Western civilization" (Андрић 1995: 10). Andrić then drew attention to the fact that some features that were brought to Bosnia by the Eastern conqueror found a fertile ground, i.e. numerous similarities were found between Turks and the spiritual features of the natives. After all, apart from the Turkish element, "the education of ordinary people was hindered by the intolerance and the unusually conservative spirit of the domestic Muslim element", and this "unhealthy conservativeness of the Bogomil descendants (...) was being demonstrated up to our days" (Like previous: 45). Andrić emphasised that, as the time passed, this kind of mentality of the Bosnian Muslim citizens came into opposition with the reformation carried out in the Turkey itself (Like previous). The travel writers of Western Europe also wrote about this tragic division of one portion of the Balkans Muslims between Europe and Asia, and they also mention their inability to understand that, in time, "the Turks from Turkey had completely disowned them" (West 2008: 793).

Andrić was particularly interested in the period in Bosnia when the already problematic rise of Christianity was suppressed by the Turkish invasion and the strong process of Islamisation. After having considered the influence of the Turkish reign on the life in Bosnia, Andrić stated that this Eastern conqueror "inflicted a wound upon the European people" (Андрић 1995: 5) and permanently drew "a dark line of division" between the Balkans and Europe (Like previous: 19). There are many lines and expressions from Andrić's thesis that illustrate the author's stance. According to Andrić, Islam is "the intruder from the East" (Like previous: 21), who puts Bosnia "in the yoke of the East" and enforces "the stone wall" between Bosnia and Europe (Like previous: 19). This is "the wall of division" which separates "Serbo-Croatian complex of race and language in two" and which "forces far into the future" (Like previous: 26). This religion was brought to Balkans by the Turks "a warlike

⁵ His thesis was presented in Austria, shortly after the ruin of Austro-Hungarian Empire and at the time of forming the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, when Andrić was a young Yugoslav diplomat. In the later, Communist Yugoslavia it was notorious and unwanted, so it was not translated and published until 1982, after the Josip Broz's death.

⁶ In certain aspects, this religion must have been similar to the old pagan religion of the Slavic people, and this is what Andrić refers to (Андрић 1995: 19). The linguists as well proved that the Slavs, back in the distant, pre-slavic era, were closer to the East than the West (Трубцекој 2004: 85-89).

Asian nation”, “a conquering nation, alien according to religion, spirit and race” (Like previous: 25). They foster “blind obedience” and faith that “resembles fanaticism” (Like previous: 22) and their influence on Bosnia and other regions was “absolutely negative” and it caused “deterioration in every respect” (Like previous: 50). Therefore, Andrić wrote, the spiritual life of Islamized Bosnians “stoned (...) into the shape of the alien religion and the unknown language” (Like previous: 85), so that the influence of Islam in the domain of culture and schooling here was “extremely inhibiting and infertile” (Like previous: 86).⁷ The similar kind of pessimistic and biting remarks were also found in the works of some European intellectuals. “The Turks destroyed the Balkans, they demolished it to the extent that it might be impossible for the consequences to be restored”, said R. West (2008: 798).

On the other hand, it seems that, as an intellectual, Andrić himself was also torn from time to time between the values of the Balkans and Europe, not accepting easily certain achievements of the European society. In that sense, for example, his negative attitude towards the Roman Catholicism and “the Catholic propaganda” is extremely prominent, as opposed to his affinity towards the Catholic Franciscan order in Bosnia (Андрић 1995: 19). In one of the letters he sent to his female friend in Rome in 1920, Andrić calls the Catholic capital “The dark nest of Pope’s” (according to Брајовић 2004:84). This attitude towards Vatican Andrić might have inherited from Bosnian Franciscans who had, as Andrić wrote in his thesis, arisen on numerous occasions against “the Roman justice” (Андрић 1995: 58, cf. 16). He consolidated this attitude towards the Catholic church using some historical information, e.g. those that show that Đurađ Branković, a Serbian despot, having to choose between the Turkish sultan and a Hungarian Hunjadi, decided to make an alliance with the Turkish sultan, since this alliance allowed him to maintain his Orthodox religion (Like previous: 21).⁸ (History will later on witness many cases of returning the Serbian refugees from Austro-Hungarian Empire back to Serbia under the Turkish rule.) However, Andrić’s attitude towards Vatican was consistent with those of some European intellectuals of that time. Therefore, R. West pointed out that Vatican conducted wrong moves regarding the Orthodox people and Bogomils, and she concludes: “If there hadn’t been for the intolerance of the papal state, Turkey wouldn’t have spent five hundred years in Europe” (West 2008: 236, cf. 192, 646). “It is possible”, she says, “that Rome destroyed much greater number of human achievements than it stimulated the creation of the new ones” (Like previous: 821). During the World War I, A. Reiss, the professor at the University in Lozano, criticized the attitude that Rome had towards the Orthodox Serbs “as heretics” (according to

⁷ In his studies, Andrić noticed many legal restrictions which made the life of Christians under the Turks very difficult. Among many of those regulations, there were some which prescribed what kind and colour of clothes the Christians in Turkey had to wear (Андрић 1995: 38), and it differed significantly from the light and multicoloured clothing which was worn on the Serbian Medieval court.

⁸ There are some information proving that, apart from offering military defence and land owning, the Turks also offered the Bogomils “full religious freedom under the condition that they count as Muslim and not Christians” (West 2008: 236).

Радић 2005: 204). The fact that all of those works, including Andrić's thesis, were not available for the readers in the Communist Yugoslavia for a very long time, may seem illogical, but only at first glance.

After all this being stated, it is not difficult to understand the occasional distrust towards Europe that occurred among the Serbs. The attitude of Europe, especially England, towards the very first Serbian liberation movements in the early 19th century, was evidently cold.⁹ R. West wrote that the British travel writers between 1805 and 1914 confidently claimed that "Bosnians and Herzegovinians were in a much better position, first under the Turks and then under the Austro-Hungarians, than the free Serbs" (West 2008: 321, cf. 636). There are some similar critical remarks in Andrić's thesis, in which he criticizes positions of the two German historians who regard the Turkish influence on the South Slavs as positive – because the Turks "forced them into the desperate fight for survival" and helped them to "get to know the Arabian and Persian handicrafts and the skill of craft" (according to Андрић 1995: 50). Andrić found this last remark acceptable only "for a superficial observer and an admirer of everything that is colourful and unusual" (Андрић 1995: 50).¹⁰ This attitude that Europe had towards the Balkans could be understood only if you remember the deeply rooted prejudices about the Balkans, which is seen as a symbol of everything backward, primitive and barbarian – this has been and still is the stance of many European intellectuals (cf. Todorova 1999: 15).

However, if Europe perceived rebellions against the Turks in Serbia with suspicion, with fear that a third great force might interfere (primarily the Orthodox Russia), majority of the Balkan Slavs perceived the rebellions as a hope for their freedom. Nevertheless, the attitude of Serbs living in the surrounding countries (e.g. Bosnia) towards these rebellions was clear, which is well depicted in Andrić's literary works (e.g. in his novel *The Bridge on the Drina*, chapter VI).¹¹ To these people who pinned their hopes to the rebellions in Serbia, Andrić also added the Bosnian Catholic-Franciscans, who had always, at least in their souls, been "on the side of Christian liberators" although they had "to act otherwise" (Андрић 1995: 59). In her works, R. West drew attention to the ancient bonds between the Franciscans and the Medieval Serbian monasteries (West 2008: 735), and these bonds will later be analysed by other authors (cf. Екмечић 1994: 130-131).

⁹ R. West wrote that in the eyes of Anglo-Saxons, "The Balkans represents the Middle East, or at least one portion of it" (West 2008: 906). Many other references that put the Balkans in the special position between the East and West, also serve as a proof of this. Some of those references also come from the East, and the good illustration of this is the very name of the organization that prepared this conference (Korean Association of Central and Eastern European and Balkan Studies).

¹⁰ However, the "admirers" of this kind are numerous in Europe. Fifteen years ago I myself witnessed this kind of European attitude towards the Balkans, when the participants of the Macedonian seminar for foreign Slavists, mostly young people from Europe, were brought to visit the Museum of Modern Art in Skopje. Majority of them rather went to visit a mosque in the neighbourhood.

¹¹ According to the first census in Bosnia in Herzegovina (1879), 43% of the population were Orthodox, while 18% were Catholic (Екмечић 1994: 131). In the last decades, over 30% of population in Bosnia and Herzegovina are Serbs (Vlahović 1984).

There are, thus, numerous similarities between Andrić's opinions presented in his thesis and those of R. West who left a great number of travel notes exactly from those areas "where Asia meets Europe" (West 2008: 652). Among others there is, for example, an opinion that the Turkish social institutions and customs "represent the negation of any form of Christian culture" (Андрић 1995: 25), i.e. that the Slavs were aware "that Christianity is better for people than Islam" (West 2008: 687), that the life under Turkish reign was "cruel and lead without any wishes" (Андрић 1995: 50), i.e. that it was a particular kind of "demoralization that the Turks brought to Europe" (West 2008: 784), that the Turkish country flourished in economy, management, and military mainly owing to the foreigners who came from conquered countries (Андрић 1995: 31, West 2008: 605), that during the Turkish reign the Serbs and Croats were separated by the civilization's "wall of division" (Андрић 1995: 26) so they were "forced to tear down the wall of lies between them" (West 2008: 680), etc.

3. Andrić's literary work

Andrić's literary work also reflected his interest in issues of clashes and intersections of civilisations on the Balkans. The tone of his literary works often coincides with his historic research observations. As he wrote a literary essay about the Serbo-Montenegrin bishop P.P. Njegoš, Andrić pointed out that the collision between the Turks and Njegoš's Serbian people (Serbs) "was not just the collision between the two religions, nations and races, it was the collision of two forces, the East and West" (Андрић 1935: 15). Andrić wrote that in the eyes of Njegoš, a bishop and a ruler, "the great and powerful Ottoman Empire truly represented hell on Earth", "the Evil incarnate" against which Njegoš had to fight "without hesitation and resignation, and with no hope of achieving the victory" (Like previous).¹² The expressions Andrić used here are practically identical to those in his thesis: "The wild Asian hordes" came from the East (Like previous: 16) to build "a bloody wall" which divided one national entity (Like previous: 15), etc.

In this clash of civilizations Andrić anticipated a new kind of anthropological intersections that occur among the people on the borders. In an essay dedicated to Vuk Karadžić, Andrić emphasised that Karadžić had presented, unlike anyone before him, the sufferings and the wild life in Balkans, – "the Turkish cruelty of our people displayed among themselves, which was transplanted to our sentimental rashness" (Андрић 1946: 80). This is the exact ground on which Andrić, with the intuition of a grand artist, sought for that particular thread of fate that came out of those social relations. It was "the two-folded tragedy that had been tearing Njegoš apart" (Андрић 1935: 21), who fought against the "savage Asian hordes" whose Islamic religion was adopted, by that time, by a

¹² R. West drew attention to this ethical principle in the Serbian history on several occasions in her book (2008: 685, 857-858 etc.).

certain number of his own people. It was “the geometry of fate” (Like previous: 31) whose paths Andrić strived to capture in his work. This is why a certain mythological and primal component in his works is easily detected, and it sometimes flows from one piece of work into another. In his essay about Njegoš, Andrić presented the Serbo-Montenegrin bishop “as a kind of ancient archpriest” (Like previous), almost the same as he presented the Serbian priest Nikola in the novel *The bridge on the Drina*, to whom he had given nearly a mythological and paternalistic role, since he seems to have been a priest “from primeval, ancient times when the world was not yet divided into different religions and churches of our time” (Андрић 1955: 149).

The tones used when referring to the deep wounds inflicted upon the European civilization by the Turkish conquering of Constantinople, would find their way into Andrić’s literary themes, but in much more subtle and reserved fashion (cf. Аврамовић 1994). The writer was also concerned here with the historic misfortune of the people on borderline between the East and West, the people “left before the gates of civilization and condemned to bear the sign of exile for eternity” (Палавестра 1991: 79). This theme of civilization in the Serbian literature concerned Ivo Andrić the most. For one to understand to what extent the writer’s eye was an indefatigable witness of the confined life of Christians under the Turkish (Muslim) reign, it would be enough just to glance at Andrić’s first short story *The journey of Alija Djerzelez*.

Andrić’s keen spirit perceived the smallest differences in the culture of these people, which he had already elaborated on in his thesis. Through the portrait of the lead heroine in the novel *The woman from Sarajevo*, he depicted, on the economic level, for example, the clash of two ideas - the Eastern one, which he considered to be slower and chaotic (cf. Андрић 1995: 45), and the Western which is embodied in the lead heroine, a woman of action, abhorred by the people from town.¹³ Andrić aimed at depicting a similar attitude towards certain kinds of art in his works. In the novel *The Chronicles of Travnik*, the idea of a European painter, and painting in general in the Muslim Bosnia was not in accordance with the teachings and philosophy of Islam, nor Bogomils, who condemn painting of pictures and icons (cf. Андрић 1995: 17).¹⁴ In this novel, he also pointed at the specific view of the Eastern culture regarding the sense of poetry and poets who were seen as a special kind of “dervishes and bigots who recite resonant verses”, and a certain number of literary critics from the East accepted this only in part (Ким 1998: 180; see 4).

However, the main characteristics of this oriental life in Bosnia included a specific kind of oriental cruelty which the people never encountered before, different forms of suffering and punishment

¹³ R. West wrote about the Turkish reign in the Balkans: “They had never made any kind of economic programme which was based on something else but simple robbing of their subjects, to whom they had never given anything in return” (West 2008: 605).

¹⁴ Many travel writers draw attention to this feature of the Eastern culture. R. West described adoration of Albanian-Muslims in front of the icons of the Serbian monastery Dečani (Kosovo and Metohija), “for the sake of health”, despite the fact that “Islam forbids presenting human faces on paintings” (West 2008: 739).

which are considered not to have existed in the pre-Ottoman period in the Balkans (cf. West 2008: 644-645, 647, 687). This might have prompted Andrić to attempt to depict this clash of civilizations in the oriental Bosnia, using exactly this kind of literary motives, and also, above all, to present “scenes of human bestiality”, to which he “gives the attire of East” (Ким 1998: 33). A good illustration is a naturalistic scene of punishing the Bosnian Serb Radisav by impaling him on the pole, a punishment unknown to the Slavs and Christians in general. Although his friends from Belgrade tried to convince him to alleviate the naturalistic details he used in describing this scene, Andrić refused to do so:

“...Without another word the peasant lay down as he had been ordered, face downward. The gypsies approached him and the first bound his hands behind his back; then they attached a cord to each of his legs, around the ankles. Then they pulled outwards and to the side, stretching his legs wide apart. Meanwhile Merdjan placed the stake on two small wooden chocks so that it pointed between the peasant legs. Then he took from his belt a short broad knife, knelt beside the stretched-out man and leant over him to cut away the cloth of his trousers and to widen the opening through which the stake would enter his body. This most terrible part of the bloody task was, luckily, invisible to the onlookers. They could only see bound body shudder at the short and unexpected prick of the knife, than half rise as if it were going to stand up, only to fall back again at once, striking dully against the planks. As soon as he had finished, the gipsy leapt up, took the wooden mallet and with slow measured blows began to strike the lower blunt end of the stake. Between each two blows he would stop for a moment and look first at the body in which the stake was penetrating and than at the two gypsies, reminding them to pull slowly and evenly. The body of the peasant, spread eagled, writhed convulsively...”¹⁵

However, even much later, when the Turks had already begun to leave the Balkans, since Austria-Hungary received the mandate to invade Bosnia and Herzegovina in 1878, the reign of cruelty was still present in Bosnia. Progress was completely absent from all the spheres of life in Bosnia, e.g. in agriculture, since Austria-Hungary “used all its forces to prolong the existence of this piece of the Medieval land in the middle of Europe” (Андрић 1961: 132), making the social unrest even larger. Andrić dealt with this topic in his *Story of Siman the Serf*, which depicts the same misfortunes of the local people even under the European rulers. This is reminiscent of the Tahir Bay’s words, a character from *The Bosnian Chronicles* – about the tendency of the European Christians: Wherever they should spread their powers, they bring wars between Christians themselves. These ominous tones are

¹⁵ Translation taken from Ivo Andrić’s “The Bridge on the Drina”, first English edition in Yugoslavia in 2003 in hard cover. By Dereta Publishers, Belgrade, Yugoslavia, translation by Lovett F. Edwards.

prevalent in the works of R. West who represented Austro-Hungarian Empire as the descendant of the Turks in the Balkans, and also as “the most terrifying horror of them all” (West 2008: 672, cf. 819).¹⁶

Andrić paid special attention to the personal tragedies and the psychical self-destructiveness connected to the complex conflicts of civilizations on the Balkans. Although we can sense those tones in his essays (e.g. the one about P.P. Njegoš), they hold a special place in his novels. What occupies his mind the most is the phenomenon connected to his characters converting to Islam, especially the historic figures. Thus, the bridge on the Drina near Višegrad is the work of an Orthodox Serb, converted to Islam, called Mehmed-Pasha Sokolović; also, one of the cruel Andrić’s character, Omer-Pasha Latas is actually an Orthodox Serb from Lika. The internal conflict becomes even more tragic when projected onto the outside world and when, for example, the idea of the bridge as a certain heritage that Mehmed-pasha left to the Serbs clashes with the idea of a Serbian peasant Radisav, who perceives the building of that bridge as a symbol of the Ottoman conqueror and tyrant whose presence would last for centuries. He perceives of that bridge as the extended Turkish arm in the Balkans, which would be used for further conquering. That is a tragic sight of another painful division within the Serbian national tissue, a division in faith which brought about all the other kinds of division, like nowhere else in the world.¹⁷

4. Andrić’s critics between the East and West

Evaluating Andrić’s work according to the criterion of his position between the cultures of the East and West is not an easy task, most of all because there are no unique parameters for evaluating the culture of East as opposed to the culture of West, for example, and vice versa. Therefore, certain discrepancies that occur in perception of the “Eastern” and “Western” features of Andrić’s works are completely understandable. The discrepancy is evident in the literary criticism, directed to I. Andrić, of the Eastern authoress Ji-Hyang Kim, as well as in the work of his earlier critic I. Sekulić. Authoress I. Sekulić, for example, perceives the absence of bourgeois life in Andrić’s first short stories as a characteristic of the East, while the Korean critic claims the opposite: “If a person from Asia, maybe even Korea, was to give an analysis, he/her would definitely think that the absence of bourgeois life is the Western characteristic. Thus, the key factor is different perspective”, concludes

¹⁶ R. West wrote about the neighbouring Empires “like wolves sitting around in a circle on their hind legs, waiting (...) for the hour when the Turks would limp back leaving their prey unprotected” and who “never had forgiven the people of the Balkans for standing up at that very hour, feeling the old dream coming to life again, and took what belonged to them” (Like previous: 834). A. Reiss, as a direct participant in the World War I in the Balkans, depicted Austria-Hungary as an aggressive, uncivilized and genocidal country (cf. Радич 2005: 203).

¹⁷ Using the example of the brothers Sokolović (Mehmed and Makarije), R. West wrote about the complex notion of “outcasts” among the Serbs, and she emphasized that “there are no pieces of written evidence about what actually happened inside those people’s souls” (West 2008: 725, cf. also 753, 755).

the Korean critic (Ким 1998: 43). As an example of another Eastern characteristic, I. Sekulić mentions the fact that the lead characters in Andrić's works are always men (1923: 247), while J. Kim gives certain examples from the Eastern literature (Chinese, Korean, Japanese), but also from Andrić's works, which prove otherwise (1998: 43, 117). I. Sekulić recognizes the oriental "erotic pains" directed towards women in the characters of Andrić's works (1923: 248), while J. Kim points out that this feature cannot be considered to belong exclusively to the Oriental culture, and that, after all, in *Ex Ponto*, Andrić himself "expressed similar excitement related to the mystery of women and female body" (1998: 44).¹⁸ Etc.

In her monograph, J. Kim emphasizes that it was not difficult for her to sense "the reduction of meaning that the East bears in Andrić's works and Serbian literature in general" (1998: 5). In fact, on several occasions in her work she puts the stress on the fact that in Andrić's works the notion of East, in cultural sense, implies "the world of Islam" i.e. the Ottoman Empire, as opposed to "the Christian world" (Like previous: 5, 39), which leads to the conclusion that the East-West distinction is relative (Like previous: 153).¹⁹ There are also some valuable social and historical parallels between Korea and the Balkans which she mentions in her monograph, for example the one about the provinces of South Korea in which people are divided, mainly for political reasons (Like previous: 10-11). There is also a similar case concerning the Serbian and Korean language, both of which preserved, until the present day, the influence of their previous rulers – the Turkish words in Serbian, the Chinese and Japanese words in Korean (Like previous: 27), etc.

However, in her observations of the East-West cultural opposition, J. Kim has a keen eye for the virtual exoticism and inspiration that East provides to the European artists (cf. ref. 10). Peter, the monk, said about Asia Minor, that it is exactly there where he "encountered all the evils that may lie in ambush, waiting for all the living creatures" (*The damned yard*), and she interpreted it in the following way: "This is because the East can offer to a Western storyteller a space that doesn't put boundaries on his imagination, since this is the space of mystery both to the storyteller and his readers, so he might feel that even the most unthinkable is possible in this place" (Ким 1998: 105).

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¹⁸ However, it is possible that Andrić might have inherited a certain portion of the Oriental life in his homeland, Bosnia.

¹⁹ Obviously, it is not easy to speak freely about the cultural relations in a situation where each individual is a product of certain cultural milieu, which implies necessary subjectivity, including even certain prejudices. Thus, in her monograph, J. Kim herself gave her evaluation of Western culture, from her point of view, in the short story *Love in a small town*. J. Kim's aim was to interpret the tragic ending of a love relationship – with the death of a girl Rifka – through the perspective of cultural differences. She might have also been carried away by the tragic tone of this patriarchal story. According to her, the girl Rifka and the oriental town represent the East, on one hand, while "the frivolous Ledenik with his arrogant superiority in relation to the Oriental 'natives'" represents the West – thus he acts "as an arrogant Westerner" (1998: 124).

In his works, Andrić dealt with the issues related to the meeting of the East and West in the Balkans in various ways, while at the same time presenting new questions about the boundary between these civilizations and its nature. It is difficult to give an answer to the question where exactly was Andrić's place as a man, scientist, diplomat and a writer in this milieu of the Balkans, and the answer itself must be complex. However, one may get the impression that Andrić's positions as an intellectual were very close to those of some liberal European circles which do not seem, though, to have been the representatives of a general European social, political and cultural ideas at the same time. This was actually the approach of a true intellectual liberty and a clear national unity which was also distant from any form of political totalitarianism. This approach was prominent among some of the top-class European intellectuals, including R. West²⁰ whose texts bear remarkable resemblance to Andrić's texts.

Perhaps, then, it is easier to understand the fact that, at the time of political difficulties in the Balkans after World War II, from a newly formed totalitarian, communist country, just Ivo Andrić was nominated – and elected – as a Nobel prize winner.²¹

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²⁰ In her texts, R. West expresses bitter opponent of communism and fascism (cf. ref. 5). She holds Europe responsible not only for pushing the small Balkan countries into the hands of Turkey and Austria-Hungary, but also because, after World War II, these countries would “fall prey to the tyranny of communism” (West 2008: 879).

²¹ Josip Broz Tito, who was the Yugoslavian president at the time, openly expressed his dissatisfaction with the fact that I. Andrić won the Nobel Prize over M. Krleža (Ћосић 2002: 94) (cf. ref. 5).

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<Abstract>

Ivo Andrić between the East and West Cultural draft

Prvoslav Radić

Ivo Andrić (Travnik 1892 - Belgrade 1975) was Serbian writer and Nobel Prize winner for Literature ("Bridge on the Drina", 1961). The material for his works was mainly drawn from the history, folklore and culture of his native Bosnia. This region was firstly ruled by the Turks for centuries, afterwards becoming Austro-Hungarian from the second half of the 19th century on. As very young man, Andrić paid special attention to the history and culture of Balkan, before all Bosnia. In 1924, he defended his PhD dissertation in Graz (Austria), on topic - "The development of spiritual life in Bosnia under the influence of Turkish reign" ("Die Entwicklung des geistigen Lebens in Bosnien unter der türkischen Herrschaft").

Bosnia as a homeland, placed on the civilization border between the East and the West, found a permanent place in Andrić's literary and scientific works. In his dissertation he described the period when Bosnia was under the Turks as "the five-century flood", "the separation wall", which "leads to the loss of customs and to the degradation in every sense". Here he describes the life of Orthodox Serbs, Catholics and Hebrews in Bosnia, and also the life of the population which had to accept Islam because of the social privileges. These facts which talk about the tragic collisions of different worlds and their cultures will find their places in Andrić's literary works too. Here he is also preoccupied with historical position of Bosnia, placed on the very border between Turkey and Europe. Andrić pointed at the tragic confrontations of different cultures on the Balkans, which never ceased to exist all these centuries.

<Key words>

Ivo Andrić, Nobel prize winner, Serbian literary, Culture, The East, The West, Civilizations.

<주제어>

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